

A REVIEW on NASAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT: Intranasal drug delivery offers the advantage of bypassing the gastrointestinal tract and avoiding first-pass metabolism in the liver, making it a promising option for enhancing the bioavailability of drugs. The highly vascularized and permeable nasal mucosa facilitates rapid absorption, allowing for a quicker onset of action. This non-invasive route is not only suitable for local treatments but also proves effective for systemic therapy, directly entering the systemic circulation. Furthermore, absorption of large molecules can be enhanced with the use of absorption promoters, contributing to the versatility of intranasal drug delivery.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nasal administration generally used for therapeutic purposes since from centuries. Nasal therapy is also called as 'Nasya karma'. It is the most convenient and reliable route, not only for local but also for systemic administration of drugs and the nasal route provides the faster and higher level of drug absorption with the possibility of self-administration. Hydrophobic and low molecular drugs can easily be permeable through the nasal mucosa with less degradation. Localised drug delivery is usually used to treat the conditions such as congestion, rhinitis and such related allergic reactions.^[1]

In recent decades the interest and importance of systemic effects of drug administered have been expanded. The nasal route has the low metabolic environment has potential to overcome limitation of oral route and duplicate the benefits of intravenous administration. Drugs ranging from small chemicals to large macromolecules including peptide/protein therapeutics, hormones and vaccines are delivered through nasal cavity^[2]. To improve the nasal absorption of drug it is necessary to improve the residence time. Various pharmaceutical dosage forms including gels, solutions, suspensions, emulsions and micro particles are used to achieve the systemic drug actions.

A. Advantages for nasal drug delivery system

- A non-invasive route and easy for administration.
- Rapid onset of action.
- Hepatic first pass metabolism was absent.
- Side effects are low due to low dose.
- The Bioavailability of larger drug molecules can be improved with the help of absorption enhancer or other approach.
- Better nasal bioavailability for smaller drug molecules.
- Convenient route when compared to parenteral route for long term therapy.
- It can be directly transported into systemic circulation and CNS is possible.
- Availability of large nasal mucosal surface area for drug absorption.
- Does not have any complex formulation requirement.
- A self – administration is possible.
- Bypasses the Blood Brain Barrier.
- Offers lower risk even for overdose.
- In GIT the degradation was avoided.
- Unsuitable drug candidates for oral route can be given successful given via nasal route.
- Patient convenience and compliance is improved.^[3]

B. Disadvantages of nasal drug delivery system

- Nasal cavity provides smaller surface area
- surfactants employed as chemical enhancers dissolve effectively at high concentrations.
- Due to improper technique of administration the mechanical loss of dosage forms takes place into other parts like respiratory tract.^[4]

C. Limitations for nasal drug delivery

- The histological toxicity of absorption enhancers used in nasal drug delivery is not yet established.
- Delivery volume in nasal cavity is restricted about 25-200 μ L.
- Irritation of nasal mucosa drugs by Budesonide, Azilactine.
- Possibility of nasal irritation hence inconvenient compared to oral route.

- Smaller absorption surface compared to GIT.
- For local side effects there is a risk of irreversible damage of the cilia of the nasal mucosa, both the substances from constituents from the dosage form.
- Relatively inconvenient to patients to oral delivery system since there is a possibility of nasal irritation.
- Large interspecies variability is absorbed in this route
- Enzymatic barrier to permeability of drug.
- Adversely affected by pathological conditions.
- By this route higher molecular compounds cannot be delivered. (mass cut off ~1 kDa).
- There could be loss of mechanical loss of dosage form into other parts of respiratory tract like lungs because of improper technique of administration. ^[5]

D. An ideal drug candidate for nasal delivery

- Low dose, generally 25mg per dose.
- Suitable stability characteristics.
- No toxic nasal metabolites.
- No nasal irritation from drug.
- No offensive odours/aromas from the drug.
- Suitable clinical rationale for nasal dosage forms e.g. onset of action.
- Appropriate aqueous solubility to provide desired dose in a 250-150ml volume of formulation and administration per nostril. ^[6]

II. ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY OF NASAL CAVITY

The nose is known to be the primary entrance to the respiratory tract, where it allows the entry of the air through respiration. In humans and in other animals breathing and olfaction is the major function. Nasal cavity has mucus layers and hairs, those which helps in the process of filtration of particles which are present in the inhaled air. The total volume is about 15ml. ^[7]

pH of mucosal secretions:

- In children – 5.0 to 6.7 (19-20)
- In adult – 5.5 to 6.5 (19-20)

Human nasal cavity has three functional areas

- Vestibular
- Olfactory and
- Respiratory areas

The vestibular part is known to be narrowest part of the nasal cavity and it is the anterior part of the nose. It provides a baffle system and useful for filtering of airborne particles, and it has keratinized and squamous epithelial cells along with nasal hairs and has poor permeability of drugs. ^[8]

The respiratory area is the lateral part of the nose and represents the largest area. In humans the respiratory area makes up to 80-90%, while in rodents it only covers 50% of the nasal cavity. It contains mainly four types of different cells:

- Goblet cells which secrete mucin for mucus layer
- Ciliated columnar cells
- Non – ciliated columnar cells
- Basal cells ^[9]

The Olfactory region comprising about 8% of the total surface area of the nasal epithelium and it is made up off non-ciliated, pseudostratified columnar epithelium. It is most important for transporting the drugs to brain and cerebrospinal fluid ^[10,11]. Figure represents the structure and composition of olfactory mucosa:

A. External nose:

- It is the visible portion that projects from the face.
- Skeleton is Cartilaginous and the external part of the nose that extends from root of the nose to the apex of nose is called **Dorsum**.
- The inferior surface is generally pierced by two piriform openings called **Nares**.
- The superior bony part of the nose, including roots, are covered by thin skin.

NOSE ANATOMY

FIG.1
FIG.2 HUMAN NOSE ANATOMY

EXTERNAL

III. DIFFERENT FACTORS AFFECTING ON NASAL DRUG ABSORPTION

Various factors affect bioavailability of nasally administered drugs as follows:

A. Biological Factors

Biological factors play a significant role in influencing the effectiveness of nasal drug delivery systems. These factors encompass various physiological aspects of the nasal cavity and the body's response to the administered drugs.

- Structural features
- Biochemical changes

B. Physiological factors

Physiological factors play a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of nasal drug delivery systems. These factors encompass various aspects of the body's physiological processes that influence drug absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion when drugs are administered intranasally.

- Blood supply and neuronal regulation
- Nasal secretions
- Mucociliary clearance and ciliary beat frequency
- Pathological conditions

C. Physicochemical Properties of Formulation

The physicochemical properties of nasal drug formulations significantly impact drug absorption, efficacy, and safety. These properties determine the behaviour of the formulation within the nasal cavity and its interactions with nasal mucosa.

- Physical form of formulation
- pH
- Osmolarity

D. Physicochemical Properties of Drugs

The physicochemical properties of a drug are fundamental determinants of its behaviour within the nasal cavity and its subsequent absorption into systemic circulation. These properties profoundly influence drug solubility, permeability, stability, and interactions with nasal mucosa.

- Molecular weight
- Size
- Solubility
- Lipophilicity
- p^{ka} and Partition coefficient^[12,13]

IV. FORMULATIONS BASED ON NASAL DELIVERY SYSTEM

A. Nasal drops

Nasal drops are one of the most simple and convenient nasal delivery systems. It has been reported that nasal drops deposit human serum albumin in the nostrils more efficiently than the nasal sprays.

B. Nasal gels

Nasal gels are high viscosity thickened solutions or suspensions. Until the recent development of precise dosing and devices, there was not much interesting this system.

C. Nasal sprays

Administering medication or clearing nasal passages can be achieved by introducing a fine mist of liquid drops into the nose using a specialized device.

D. Nasal emulsions

Intranasal emulsions, though less studied than other nasal delivery systems, can provide advantages for local applications due to viscosity reform in sensitive areas. Saline nasal spray remains a common choice for relieving nasal congestion, while flu vaccines in nasal spray form aim to enhance immunization efficacy.^[14,15]

V. POLYMERS USED IN INTRANASAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

A. Temperature responsive polymers in Nasal Drug Delivery

Poloxamer 407 which is thermosensitive polymer frequently used for in situ gelation. It is a non-ionic surfactant consists of poloxyethylene - polyoxypropylene copolymers. At a given temperature when poloxamer is dispersed in aqueous phase above the critical micellar concentration, there is formation of micelles with hydrophilic shell and hydrophobic core. Thermoreversible gelling properties of various polymers grades depends upon the molecular weight of hydrophilic core to molecular weight of hydrophobic core. Polaxomer 407 aqueous solution 16 to 18 %exhibited thermoresponsive gelling at 32+2, which is closer to nasal temperature.^[17]

Some of the temperature responsive polymers are:

- Carbopol 934P
- HPMC K-15
- Chitosan
- Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (NaCMC)
- Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC)
- Hydroxypropyl cellulose and methylcellulose

B. PH responsive polymers

Ion responsive polymers generally have ionisable groups. Polymeric systems with distinct rheological behaviour display gelation triggered by temperature changes and cation-induced interactions, showcasing unique characteristics upon coulombic interaction with oppositely charged species. Upon complexation with cations and hydrogen bonding with water, there is formation of double helical junction zones and a three-dimensional network responsible for *in situ* gelling.^[18] some of the P^H responsive polymers are:

- Poly methacrylic acid
- polyethylene glycol (P(MAA-g-EG)) and
- Polyvinyl acetal diethylamino acetate

C. Mucoadhesive polymers

1. *Cellulose derivatives*: Various pharmaceutical grade derivatives of cellulose are extensively employed across different administration routes, with several proving effective in enhancing intranasal drug absorption. Soluble cellulose derivatives like hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC), methylcellulose (MC), and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), alongside insoluble ones such as ethyl cellulose and microcrystalline cellulose (MCC), are notable examples. These derivatives play crucial roles in improving drug delivery and efficacy through nasal routes.

The mucoadhesive property of cellulose derivatives significantly prolongs the residence time of drugs in the nasal cavity^[19]. Moreover, their high viscosity upon hydration in the nasal cavity allows for sustained drug release^[20]. Consequently, utilizing celluloses as absorption enhancers can lead to enhanced intranasal absorption and increased bioavailability. Numerous references demonstrate the effectiveness of celluloses in enhancing the intranasal bioavailability of both small hydrophobic and hydrophilic macromolecular drugs (see Table 1). For instance, apomorphine administered nasally with CMC achieved a relative bioavailability of 102% compared to subcutaneous injection in rabbits. Another study showed that ketorolac tromethamine administered with MCC could achieve an absolute bioavailability of up to 90.77%. Furthermore, peptide drugs like leuprolide and FD-4, when dosed with MCC/HPC through the nasal route, reached absolute bio availabilities of 34.9% and 35.5% in rabbits, respectively.

2. *Chitosan*: Chitosan, a linear cationic polysaccharide derived from the deacetylation of chitin found in crustacean shells, contains NH₂ groups, rendering it insoluble at neutral and alkaline pH. However, it can form water-soluble salts with various acids like glutamic, hydrochloric, lactic, and acetic acid. Toxicity tests have shown that the LD₅₀ of chitosan in mice exceeds 16 g/kg (Paul and Garside, 2000). Due to its affordability, biodegradability, and biocompatibility, chitosan is increasingly utilized as a pharmaceutical excipient in oral, ocular, nasal, implant, parenteral, and transdermal drug delivery applications.^[21]

VI.METHODS INVOLVED IN INTRANASAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

A. Solution/Suspension Formulation

Dissolving or suspending the drug in a liquid form suitable for nasal administration.

B. Sprays

Formulating drugs as nasal sprays, often using propellants or pump mechanisms for controlled delivery.

C. Powder Formulation

Creating dry powder formulations that can be administered using nasal inhalers or insufflators.

D. Gels

Developing drug-containing nasal gels for sustained release and improved drug retention.

E. Nanoparticles/ Liposomes

Incorporating drugs into nanoparticles or liposomes for enhanced stability, solubility, and targeted delivery.

F. Microemulsions

Formulating drugs in stable oil-in-water or water-in-oil emulsions for improved absorption.

G. In Situ Gelling Systems

Utilizing formulations that undergo gelation upon contact with nasal mucosa, enhancing drug residence time

VII. EVALUATION OF NASAL DRUG FORMULATIONS

A. *In vitro* nasal permeation studies

Diverse methods are commonly employed to assess the diffusion of drugs through the nasal mucosa from a given formulation. There are two different methods to study about diffusion profile of the drugs

1. *In vitro* diffusion studies: The *in vitro* diffusion studies use a glass nasal diffusion cell. This cell consists of a water-jacketed recipient chamber with a 60 ml capacity and a flanged top of about 3mm. The lid of the chamber has three openings for sampling, a thermometer, and a donor tube chamber. The donor chamber is 10 cm long with an internal diameter of 1.13 cm, and it also has a flanged top of about 3mm, with three openings in the lid for sampling and a thermometer.

The sheep's nasal mucosa was removed from the underlying bony tissues and immersed in distilled water with a small amount of gentamicin injection. Once blood is entirely removed from the mucosal surface, it is affixed to the donor chamber tube, ensuring it lightly contacts the diffusion medium in the recipient chamber. At scheduled intervals, 0.5 ml samples are taken from the recipient chamber, transferred to amber ampoules, and replaced with new samples. The drug content in the withdrawn samples is assessed using an appropriate analytical method. The temperature is consistently maintained at 37°C throughout the experiment.

2. *In vivo* nasal absorption studies: The rat is anesthetized using intraperitoneal injection of sodium pentobarbital. An incision is made in the neck, and a polyethylene tube is inserted into the trachea. Another tube is placed through the oesophagus toward the back of the nasal cavity. The nasopalatine tract is sealed to prevent the drug solution from draining through the mouth. The drug solution is introduced into the nasal cavity through the nostril or cannulation tubing. From the femoral vein the blood samples are collected. By blocking potential drainage routes, the drug can only be absorbed and transported into the systemic circulation through penetration and/or diffusion across the nasal mucosa.

B. Rabbit model

The rabbit serves as a suitable model for nasal absorption studies due to various advantages. Firstly, it allows for pharmacokinetic studies similar to larger animals such as monkeys. Secondly, it is cost-effective, easily accessible, and simple to maintain in laboratory conditions. Additionally, the rabbit's substantial blood volume of around 300ml enables frequent blood sampling (1-2ml), facilitating a comprehensive understanding of absorption and the determination of the pharmacokinetic profile. For drug administration in rabbits (around 3 kg), the choice between anaesthesia or consciousness depends on the study's purpose. In the anesthetized model, a combination of ketamine and xylazine is intramuscularly injected. The rabbit's head is held upright, and the drug solution is nasal sprayed into each nostril. The rabbit's body temperature is kept at 37°C using a heating pad throughout the experiment. Blood samples are collected through an indwelling catheter in the marginal ear vein or artery.

C. *Ex vivo* nasal perfusion models

In *ex vivo* nasal perfusion models, the surgical preparation mirrors that of the *in vivo* rat model. To minimize drug solution loss, a funnel is positioned between the nose and reservoir. The drug solution, maintained at 37°C, circulates through the rat's nasal cavity using a peristaltic pump. The solution exits through the nostrils, passes through the funnel, and returns to the reservoir, where it is continuously stirred.

The absorbed drug amount is determined by measuring the residual concentration in the perfusing solution.

For rabbits in *ex vivo* nasal perfusion studies, anaesthesia with parenteral urethane-acepromazine is administered. A midline neck incision is made, and a polyethylene neonatal endotracheal tube is cannulated into the trachea. The oesophagus is isolated, ligated, and fitted with flexible tubing reaching the posterior nasal cavity. To prevent drainage, the nasopalatine tract is closed with adhesive. A peristaltic pump recirculates the drug in an isotonic buffer solution. ^[14,16]

VIII. APPLICATIONS

A. Delivery of non-peptides pharmaceutical's

Small, lipophilic drugs with low molecular weight (below 1000 Daltons), particularly non-peptides, are effectively absorbed through the nasal mucosa, even without permeation enhancers. The nasal membrane, richly vascularized and featuring a large surface area due to nasal turbinate's, facilitates easy drug absorption. Drugs prone to extensive pre-systemic metabolism, such as progesterone, estradiol, propranolol, nitroglycerin, and sodium chromoglycate, exhibit rapid absorption through the nasal mucosa, achieving a systemic bioavailability of around 100%. This is attributed to the direct passage of venous blood from the nose into systemic circulation, allowing these drugs to circulate widely within minutes of dosing. Intranasally administered drugs often exhibit faster and more efficient absorption compared to oral administration, ensuring quick uptake.

Several non-peptide drugs investigated for nasal delivery with notable bioavailability include adrenal corticosteroids, sex hormones (17 β -estradiol, progesterone, norethindrone, testosterone), vitamins (B vitamins), cardiovascular drugs (hydralazine, Angiotensin II antagonist, nitro glycerine, isosorbide dinitrate, propranolol, colifilium tosylate), and autonomic nervous system agents like sympathomimetics (ephedrine, epinephrine, phenylephrine, xylometazoline, dopamine, dobutamine) and parasymphomimetics (nicotine, methacholine).

B. Delivery of peptide-based pharmaceuticals

The efficient absorption of nonpeptide, lipophilic drugs with a molecular weight below 1000 Daltons through the nasal mucosa occurs even in the absence of additional permeation enhancers. The highly vascularized nasal membrane, coupled with the ample surface area provided by nasal turbinate's, facilitates the easy absorption of these drugs. Substances susceptible to significant pre-systemic metabolism, such as progesterone, estradiol, propranolol, nitroglycerin, and sodium chromoglycate, quickly absorb through the nasal mucosa, achieving a systemic bioavailability of approximately 100%. The swift circulation of venous blood from the nose directly into the systemic circulation allows these drugs to circulate widely within minutes of administration. Intranasal drug delivery often results in faster and more efficient absorption compared to oral administration, ensuring a rapid uptake.

Several non-peptide drugs explored for nasal delivery and exhibiting noteworthy bioavailability include adrenal corticosteroids, sex hormones (17 β -estradiol, progesterone, norethindrone, testosterone), B vitamins, cardiovascular drugs (hydralazine, Angiotensin II antagonist, nitro glycerine, isosorbide dinitrate, propranolol, coli ilium to sylate), and autonomic nervous system agents such as sympathomimetics (ephedrine, epinephrine, phenylephrine, xylometazoline, dopamine, dobutamine) and parasymphomimetics(nicotine, methacholine).

C. Delivering the Drugs to Brain through Nasal Cavity

This delivery system proves advantageous for conditions like Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, or pain, where rapid and/or specific drug targeting to the brain is essential. Developing a nasal delivery system directed toward the brain enhances the proportion of the drug reaching the central nervous system (CNS) after nasal administration. The olfactory region, situated in the upper and remote parts of the nasal passages, provides an avenue for certain compounds to bypass the blood-brain barrier and enter the brain. Recent studies highlight the successful intranasal delivery of neurotrophic factors like NGF, IGF1, FGF, and ADNF to the CNS, demonstrating promising results in increasing drug bioavailability in the

brain. Human studies involving proteins such as AVP, CCK analogue, MSH/ACTH, and insulin reveal their direct delivery to the brain from the nasal cavity.

D. Delivery of Vaccines through Nasal Route

Mucosal sites serve as the primary defence against invading microorganisms. The nasal mucosa plays a crucial role in this defence by filtering pathogens from inhaled air through compaction and mucociliary clearance. The nose, along with the associated nasal-associated lymphoid tissue (NALT), functions as an effective immune system site. In humans, this combination is referred to as Waldeyer's Ring. Nasal secretions also contribute to this defence mechanism.

E. Delivery of diagnostic drugs

Nasal drug delivery systems are crucial for administering diagnostic agents, aiding in the diagnosis of various diseases and disorders within the body. The intranasal route is particularly advantageous for achieving systemic release of medicaments into the bloodstream, providing rapid results with reduced toxicity. For instance, phenolsulfonphthalein serves as a diagnostic agent for evaluating kidney function in patients. 'Secretin' is employed to diagnose pancreatic disorders in diabetic patients, while Penta gastrin is a diagnostic agent used to determine the secretory function of gastric acid. [22,23]

IX.CONCLUSION

The nasal cavity's extensive surface area and vascularized mucosa enable direct drug absorption into the bloodstream, bypassing first-pass metabolism. Nasal drug delivery is gaining traction, especially for challenging drugs, addressing manufacturing and delivery challenges. The heightened activity in this field suggests an imminent release of innovative nasal products, capitalizing on the benefits of this administration route.

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